

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D21: Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan

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Executive Summary

The CODECO Deliverable *D21 - Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* refers to the work under development in Work Package 6 and Task 6.1 - Public Dissemination and Communication. This deliverable describes the dissemination, communication, and promotion activities planned for the CODECO project which oversees the communication strategy planned and ensures a consensus-based approach in the decision-making process.

This dissemination, communication and promotion plan covers the methods used to communicate project's information, disseminate project's results, and promote CODECO achievements to the widest possible audience including academic, industrial, and business. This deliverable report will guide the project's dissemination in an efficient, effective, and coordinated way requiring the participation of all CODECO partners.

Keywords: Cloud, Communication, Dissemination, Edge, Internet of Things, Internetworking, Network Technologies, Open Source, Promotion, Software, Visibility

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List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial intelligence
AR	Academia and Research
CA	Consortium Agreement
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration
DEV	Developers
EC	European commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GA	General Audience
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project coordinator (FOR)
SDO	Standards Development Organization
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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1. Introduction

1.1 About the CODECO Project

The Internet has been going through a radical transformation to support the requirements of evolving information societies, continuously introducing new challenges to Internet services and data processing on the Cloud. These challenges are becoming urgent with the development of next generation *Internet of Things (IoT)* services. These new environments are expected to be highly mobile, involving small cell management, and large-scale deployments. Edge computing and decentralized Edge-Cloud computing architectures play a key role in the Edge-Cloud continuum, as there is also an increase in service decentralization. As such, it is necessary to re-think the design of the Edge-Cloud continuum, to provide communication and computation in scenarios involving a varying number of data producers and consumers.

In this respect, the **CODECO** project - Cognitive Decentralized Edge Cloud Orchestration - aims at addressing the challenges posed by the evolution of the Internet. The traditional design of the Edge-Cloud continuum needs to be re-thought to support the varying number of data producers and consumers. The **CODECO** framework aims to provide a cognitive and decentralized solution to support the Edge-Cloud continuum.

CODECO is a cognitive, cross-layer and highly adaptive Edge-Cloud management framework (TRL4-5) with a unique and smart orchestration approach that provides support for data management and governance decentralized data workflow. It also enables dynamic offloading of computation and adaptation of networking services.

At the core of the CODECO framework are privacy-preserving decentralized learning mechanisms to:

- i. Reduce latency and power consumption from the far Edge to Cloud.
- ii. Adjust the computation in real-time to available Edge-Cloud constraints.
- iii. Adjust running services to the needs of the application, the data sources, and the surrounding context.
- iv. Benefit from a flexible networking infrastructure that adapts to the needs of active services.
- v. Democratize the technology to faster market adoption of the toolkit, as well as products and services derived from it.

1.2 Objectives of Deliverable 21

This deliverable has been developed in the context of WP6 - Dissemination, Promotion and Standardization, led by UGOE, in Task 6.1 - Public Dissemination and Communication, led by INO.

The objectives of this Deliverable can be described as follows:

1. **Communication strategy**: to oversee the communication strategy for the project, ensuring that there is a clear and consistent approach to promote communication throughout the project.
2. **Dissemination strategy**: to outline and guide the project's dissemination activities in an efficient, effective, and coordinated way, involving all partners.
3. **Consensus-Based approach**: to ensure a decision-making process in which all decisions are made in a transparent and inclusive manner with the stakeholders.
4. **Engagement action**: to cover the needed dissemination for the project's progress to reach the widest possible audience.
5. **Target groups assessment**: to specify the target audiences ensuring that the project's results and achievements are widely known, understood and uptake by the different stakeholders, including the academic, industrial, and business communities.

1.3 Deliverable Scope

This Communication, Dissemination, and Promotion Plan will be used as a strategy to achieve the objectives of the CODECO project. By actively communicating and disseminating information about the project, we will guarantee that the CODECO results remain relevant and impactful and that its outcomes are widely known and appreciated, maximizing its impact.

This strategic plan has the purpose of:

1. **Disseminate project results**: To disseminate the results of CODECO and make them accessible to relevant stakeholders and the public. The development of communication and engagement actions such as website design or social media activities will increase interest in the project.
2. **Raise awareness to the CODECO development**: To reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that the results of the project are effectively highlighted, leading to validation, improvement and further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts, especially towards target vertical sectors, facilitating exploitation of the project's outcomes and promoting development of

innovative solutions based on CODECO outcome in order to facilitate the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and experiences.

3. **Building interest and promoting collaboration and synergies:** To create interest in the project among potential partners, investors, and other stakeholders, and to encourage them to get involved. CODECO intends to create synergies and collaborative actions with other ongoing projects to increase visibility, build partnerships and maximize impact. This will allow the establishment of a synchronised and close cooperation with relevant and broad ICT initiatives, and relevant standards groups (e.g., IETF/IRTF) as well as with open-source initiatives (e.g., Eclipse, Linux Cloud Foundation), while establishing liaisons with related projects, entities, and initiatives in research and innovation domains such as the H2020 BigDataStack¹ project, or *Cooperation and Support Actions (CSA)* such as EuEdgeCloudIoT².
4. **Fostering engagement:** To foster engagement with the wider community and ensure that the project is relevant to their needs and interests. This will cover different types of audiences such as academic communities, industry, and policymakers.
5. **Ensuring impact:** To ensure that the project has the highest possible impact and contributes to developments in the field. Exploitation strategies to outreach CODECO's results during and after the end of the project will be defined in the context of WP7.

2 Target Audience for CODCO

D21 will ensure that the project's scientific and innovation results and outcomes are effectively disseminated, across the CODECO stakeholders' groups considering the domains specifically addressed in use-cases, and beyond. The goal is to increase the visibility and impact of the project, in terms of its scientific relevance and its commercial potential.

In this respect, the CODECO project identified the possible target audiences:

- **Information and communication technologies (ICT)**, industrial and small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) players.

This group comprises vendors and integrators, both large companies and SMEs, involved in the deployment of Cloud based and Edge based solutions, technology vendors, service providers, telecommunications operators, large companies, and SMEs. The aim is to raise

¹ <https://bigdatastack.eu/>

² <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/the-csas/>

CODECO awareness and to show its performance as well as a value-add. In this context it is relevant to highlight that both the industrial partners and the research partners play a key role in the further engagement of other industry players.

- **Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers (GOV).**

This group comprises a wide group of public sector stakeholders including government agencies, regulators, municipalities, citizens, public authorities, and other organizations which benefit from a platform such as CODECO to simplify the deployment of the containerized codebase.

- **Standardization entities and open-source communities (SDO).**

Standardization entities responsible for defining and maintaining standards for various industries and technologies will ensure interoperability and compatibility with the CODECO framework. Normative, pre-normative entities and with open-source alliances and consortia will collaborate on the development and adoption of new technologies and open-source software, relevant to the CODECO ecosystem.

- **Academic and research (AR).**

Research scientists, teachers, and students in the field of computer science, engineering, and related disciplines will be a key group to spread the benefits of the CODECO concept, and to provide feedback and transfer of information, promoting scientific and technical know-how generated within the project. AR is a key group to spread the benefits of CODECO concepts and technologies, and to provide feedback to, transfer and promote the scientific and technical know-how generated within the project. This target group can be effectively reached through the consortium's research communities and partnerships with other leading research initiatives and institutions in Europe and beyond. It is relevant to highlight that both the industrial partners and the research partners play a key role in the further engagement of other industry players.

- **End-users (EUS).**

The public and specific end-users in the use-case domains (Manufacturing, Smart Cities, Energy, Smart Buildings) play a major role in the project dissemination and engagement. This group includes consumers, who are interested in learning about the latest developments in Edge-Cloud computing and IoT and how these technologies will impact their lives.

- **Developers (DEV).**

Software developers and early developers with whom CODECO shall interact via the activities developed in WP5 (use-cases), WP6 (dissemination, communication) and WP7 (community building, Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme for

third-party engagement).will also be considered to promote and test the CODECO toolkit and accelerate the integration of knowledge.

- **General Audience (GA).**

General audience may also be considered as stakeholders of CODECO. Even without a specialized background in the technical areas of the project, they may still be interested in CODECO and understanding its potential implications for society.

By considering the needs and interests of these different target audiences, this deliverable needs to be designed to ensure that the project outcomes are relevant, accessible, and engaging to its intended audience. This will certainly maximize the impact and outreach of the project.

3 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy for the CODECO project should be tailored to the specific needs of the project and its stakeholders and should be regularly reviewed and updated as needed to ensure that the project's objectives and goals are effectively communicated to the relevant audiences.

To successfully reach the main objectives of the CODECO project, online, physical, and interactive dissemination tools will be established between all the members of the consortium and specific audiences through which the project will be presented and disseminated.

Each partner of the CODECO consortium is encouraged to actively contribute to the communication and dissemination activities under the WP6 - Dissemination, Promotion and Standardization. It is expected that all partners take a part in the dissemination of the project by contributing, cooperating, and assisting in the communication methodology.

This dissemination strategy will comprise two main components: an **external communication strategy** and an **internal communication strategy** as described next.

3.1 External Strategy

3.1.1 Visual Identity of the Project

3.1.1.1 Project Logotype

The visual identity of a project is an important aspect of the project's overall communication and dissemination strategy. A strong visual identity can help the project establish a professional and recognizable brand and can be used to promote the project and its results. For the CODECO project, the visual identity was designed to reflect the core values and goals, such as innovation, adaptability, and decentralization. The design is simple, clean, and easily recognizable, and conveys a sense of technology and modernity.

The project logotype should be the cornerstone of the visual identity and should be easily recognizable and memorable. The CODECO logotype should be clearly identifiable when used in various contexts, such as on the project's website, in presentations, or promotional materials.

As such, Figure 1 represents the chosen option for the official logotype of the CODECO project.

Figure 1: The logotype of the CODECO project.

In addition to the logotype, the visual identity of the CODECO project also includes a colour palette and typography that reflect the project's values and goals. These elements should be consistent across all the project's dissemination materials and should help to reinforce the project's brand and identity. All dissemination materials of the project will take into consideration this visual identity, and it should be reviewed and approved by the project team members to ensure that it effectively represents the project and its goals.

3.1.1.2 Dissemination Materials

Effective dissemination materials ensure that the project results are clearly communicated and reach the intended audience effectively. These materials need to be designed to appeal a broad range of stakeholders, including researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and the public.

CODECO dissemination materials may include:

- Brochures and leaflets
- Infographics
- Posters
- Videos
- Multimedia content (including animations)
- Presentations
- White papers and reports
- Newsletters

Importantly, these materials will be available in a range of formats, including print and digital, to ensure that they are accessible to as many stakeholders as possible (section 5 – Table 4). The dissemination materials will be regularly updated throughout the project's lifetime, and they will be promoted through the project website, social media channels, and other dissemination activities, and available for download or distribution as required.

3.1.2 Project Website

A project website is an important tool for communicating information about the CODECO project to an audience, including potential partners, stakeholders, and interested individuals. The website should be designed to be user-friendly and visually appealing.

The CODECO project Website serves as a platform for providing information about the project's concept, impact on society, main objectives, and achieved results. The website will include information about the project's progress, consortium team members, related actions and initiatives, news and updates, a calendar of upcoming events and conferences, and a library of project-related documents such as the submitted deliverables. The Website will also feature links to the project's social media accounts and other relevant resources. A dedicated Website for the CODECO project was already created by the project coordinator (FOR): <http://he-codeco.eu/>.

Figure 2: Home page of CODECO's Website.

By providing access to information and resources related to the project, the CODECO Website creates a collaborative environment that encourages engagement and participation from a diverse range of stakeholders. The website serves as a centralized hub for project updates and outcomes, making it easy for stakeholders to stay informed and up to date. This fosters greater transparency and accountability in the project, while also supporting the dissemination and communication of project outcomes to a wider audience. The CODECO website will also play a critical role in supporting the project's success by facilitating collaboration and dissemination of research into the academic field.

The following features are included in the CODECO project website:

- i. **Home:** a brief introduction to the project concept.
- ii. **About:** a section presenting the project overview, objectives, assets, key research contributions and workplan.
- iii. **Results:** detailed information about the project's results, including deliverables, presentations, publications, and software. This could also include some more detailed info such as videos and animations to help illustrate the project's concept.
- iv. **Events:** a list of upcoming events with a search bar to find relevant events within the CODECO framework.
- v. **Gallery:** relevant photos taken in selected events of the CODECO consortium.
- vi. **Partners:** information about the project partners and their institutions.

- vii. **Contacts:** contacts of the project coordinator – Dr Rute Sofia – from Fortiss GmbH and other CODECO partners.
- viii. **Social networks:** links to directly forward the interested audience to relevant social media such as LinkedIn.

The CODECO website will be improved in the following months and regularly updated with new information and resources as the project progresses by WP6 Leader (UGOE) and Task Leaders (UGOE, INO and ECL) and FOR. Website updates will be developed periodically every 4 months. Specific actions, e.g., updates of figures or of specific content shall be done whenever required. As part of our effort to track the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination of the Website, we will measure and quantify the number visitors to the CODECO project website. These metrics can include number of visitors, pageviews, time spent on the site, bounce rate, and geographical location of visitors. By analysing these metrics, we will be able to assess the impact of the website and maybe identify areas where we need to improve our communication efforts.

The ZENODO CODECO (<https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco>) deposits all generated reports, scientific publications, etc. This community is curated by the WP6 leader (UGOE), by the T6.1 leader (INO), and by the coordinator (FOR).

Overall, the CODECO project Website serves as a central hub for information about the project and its results and should help to promote the project and its goals to wider audiences.

3.1.3 Social Media Dissemination

The Communication, Dissemination and Promotion Plan will use the project's social media tools to reach a wider audience and build a community of followers interested in the project's activities. By promoting the project via social media, it is expected that more people will become aware of the project and become involved in its activities. Additionally, using social media will drive traffic to the project website, promoting public engagement and interaction with the project or potential future partnerships. The goal is to increase the visibility and reach of the project, and to foster a sense of community and engagement among those interested in the project's outcomes.

Twitter (Figure 3) and **LinkedIn** (Figure 5) will be the major social media channels planned for the CODECO project. These social networks will allow an effective and spread

dissemination of the project news and results. The public or specific stakeholders will have quick access to the project, achieved results and other relevant details.

Table 1: CODECO presence in LinkedIn.

LinkedIn		
	<p>Account: @CODECO Project</p>	<p>About: The overall aim of CODECO is to contribute to a smoother and more flexible support of services across the Edge-Cloud continuum via the creation of a novel, cognitive Edge-Cloud management framework. CODECO will implement software toolkits suitable for the smarter management of highly distributed environments based on heterogeneous networks and integrating mobile, resource-constrained devices.</p> <p>CODECO aims at providing support for the next generation of smart services, focusing on dense deployments in B5G/6G services. For this, CODECO considers multiple use-cases across different vertical domains (Smart Cities, Manufacturing, Energy and Smart Facilities), involving mobile, far Edge devices and addressing the IoT-Edge-Cloud orchestration based on a cross-layer approach that envisions data, compute, and network adaptation.</p>
<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/codeco-project/</p>		

Figure 3: CODECO project's LinkedIn page.

A group for CODECO dissemination activities on a LinkedIn page was already created (Figure 4) and it is hosted at <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12772835/>. This will contribute to a smoother and more flexible support on the dissemination actions planned for the CODECO.

Figure 4: LinkedIn group home page of CODECO.

Table 2: CODECO presence in Twitter.

Twitter		
	<p>Account: @CodecoProject</p>	<p>About: Cognitive Decentralized Edge Cloud Orchestration - Project Funded by European Union under Grant Agreement 101092696</p>
<p>https://twitter.com/CodecoProject</p>		

Figure 4: Main Twitter page of CODECO.

Each CODECO Partner will take part in the dissemination of the project, being involved in providing inputs and sharing relevant information within the social networks, including announcements of major scientific achievements, events, or related activities/initiatives of interest. Whenever it is possible or suitable, CODECO partners should make project's announcements and share events, photos, or videos by tagging CODECO's social networks (LinkedIn and Twitter) under relevant circumstances. All Partners are also invited to share CODECO's social media publications through their own social media accounts or through their institutional communication channels. Institutions/organizations websites can also be used to publicize project activities. As such, regular news, and posts about the progress of the project or upcoming conferences should be posted regularly to ensure an efficient dissemination of CODECO.

To assist Partners in directly disseminating activities or actions related with the project, if results deriving from the project are involved, Partners need to follow the rules of the CA and processes described in Deliverable D1 (Handbook). In the case of partners that want to directly disseminate activities or actions related with the project in the CODECO's LinkedIn or Twitter, they should contact UGOE as the WP6 leader or INO as the T6.1 leader. To facilitate dissemination, CODECO counts with a google form where events and activities are collected to be then updated into the social networks.

The project will track and analyse the engagement of its social media platforms by monitoring followers, likes, shares, and comments, to understand the effectiveness of our social media outreach. This will allow the evaluation of the outreach and engagement of the CODECO project through communities.

3.1.4 Scientific Publications

Scientific and academic publications play an important role in communicating the results of the CODECO project to the research community and are critical for establishing the project's impact and reputation.

The CODECO consortium aims at publishing their findings in high-quality, peer-reviewed journals and magazines in the field of Edge-Cloud computing and the IoT, via an open science practice and making the research results accessible to both technical and non-technical audiences. Specifically, CODECO follows the *Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific*

*Publications and Research Data in Horizon Europe*³. CODECO will provide open science policy to all publications developed during the project, with papers being submitted in pre-print servers and relevant data on open repositories as well as targeting the SJR rank Q1/Q2. Regular scientific publications are expected in national, European, and international journals. An indicative list of Scientific Journals to consider for publications is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: List of some relevant scientific Journals and Magazines.

Journal/Magazine
IEEE Access
IEEE Communications Magazine
IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference
IEEE Network
IEEE Internet Computing
IEEE Internet of Things Journal
IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing
IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology
IEEE Transactions on Services Computing
IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing
IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking
ACM Transactions on Internet of Things
ACM Transactions on Internet Technology
IEEE Transactions on Networking and Service Management
IEEE JSAC
IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials
ACM Transactions on Computer Systems (ACM TOCS)
ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology
ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems
Elsevier Computer Communications
Elsevier Journal of Network and Computer Applications
Elsevier Computer Networks
Elsevier Internet of Things

³<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/content/guidelines-open-access-scientific-publications-and-research-data-horizon-2020>

Sharing the project's results with the research community will promote further discussions and collaboration in the field of Edge-Cloud computing.

3.1.5 White Papers and Presentations

White papers and presentations will be used as tools for disseminating the results and achievements of the CODECO project. They will provide an opportunity to present technical information and innovative solutions to a broader audience, including industry partners, academics, and potential end-users.

White papers, as technical reports of a specific topic, will serve as a platform to explain the rationale behind the project, present new developments, and technologies, and offer recommendations for future research, often to make information access to non-experts in the field and raise awareness of project outcomes to more general audiences.

On the other hand, presentations of the CODECO project will be done aiming at targeting specific audiences concerning the type of event, such as conferences, small talks, webinars, and workshops. They can be used to provide an overview of the project, present technical details, and results, and importantly, to engage stakeholders in discussions and promote the adoption of CODECO technologies, raise awareness about its results, and foster collaboration.

3.1.6 Public Events and Conferences

To highlight the contributions of the CODECO project, clear and engaging presentations in high-profile relevant events should be considered from the very beginning of the project. This should include industrial, academic, software developer and demonstration events.

The participation of the CODECO team in conferences and workshops related to Edge-Cloud computing, IoT, and related fields, will promote the dissemination of its research results and facilitate interaction with other experts in the field. Additional events such as community events, summer schools, webinars, and workshops must also be considered to boost knowledge transfer and/or address potential gaps.

Some examples of relevant events for the CODECO project could include:

- International conferences on Edge-Cloud computing, IoT, and decentralized systems.
- Industry events focused on Edge-Cloud computing and the IoT.

- Workshops, tutorials, and other technical events focused on specific topics such as decentralized data management.
- Public events, such as technology or innovation conferences, provide opportunities to engage with the public.

An indicative list of events including conferences, seminars, fair exhibitions and/or workshops to attend in 2023 is presented in *Table 4*. This list should be continuously updated depending on upcoming events that could be interesting for the CODECO objectives achievement. Future events on aside areas of AI or with a higher/different spectrum of topics should also be considered to attend as they can contribute positively to higher dissemination and engagement levels. These events can also provide a platform for discussion and collaboration between industry stakeholders.

Table 4: Indicative list of events to attend in 2023 concerning the dissemination and communication activities for the CODECO project.

Name of the event	Location	Date
ACM/IEEE Symposium on Edge Computing (SEC)	Wilmington, DE, USA	06.12.2023-09.12.2023
IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing (IEEE CLOUD)	Chicago, IL, United States	02.07.2023-08.07.2023
European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)	Göteborg, Sweden	06.06.2023-09.06.2023
IEEE WPMC	Tampa, Florida, USA	28.11.2023-04.12.2023
ACM MobiCom	Madrid, Spain	02.10.2023-06.10.2023
ACM SIGCOMM	New York, USA	10.09.2023-14.09.2023
IEEE ICDCS	Hong Kong	18.07.2023-21.07.2023
IEEE ICNP	Iceland	10.10.2023-14.10.2023
IEEE Network of the Future (NoF)	Izmir, Turkey	04.10.2023-06.10.2023
ACM CoNEXT	Paris, France	06.12.2023-08.12-2023
IEEE AllIoT 2023	Virtual, USA	07.06.2023-10.06.2023

In addition to events participation, the CODECO team also intends to organize several events, as follows, and represented in Figure 6:

1. An industrial event at M12, by the coordinator FOR. This will focus on research and development of the project to create awareness among companies and especially SMEs, aiming at increasing interest in the potential commercial and market value and further exploitation of the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.
2. A scientific event at M24 – a Dagstuhl seminar-, by UGOE. This event shall assist in reaching the engagement of stakeholders from academia and industry, being the value-add the possibility to increase exploitation opportunities towards decentralized learning approaches.
3. A scientific workshop at M24, by ATH, co-located with a top conference from ACM/IEEE/IFIP communities.
4. A final workshop at M34-M36, jointly organized by INO and FOR, will be held to promote feedback, interest, and potential exploitation of CODECO by show-casing the results of the project.
5. Two standardization events between M24-36, jointly organized by IBM and FOR, aimed at discussing the standardization contributions of CODECO, together with other related initiatives.
6. A demo camp/hackathon at M24, jointly organized by ECL and INO to promote the exploitation of activities and building/engagement of the community.
7. Innovation and Research community engagement programme, organized by INO, targeting SMEs, academia/research, and early developers in co-design with creatives of non-technical background, to exploit the CODECO ecosystem. The programme will be based on a series of activities/events to be developed between M16-M36.

Figure 6: Planned Activities' Timeline.

3.1.7 Engagement and Awareness Activities

CODECO communication, dissemination and promotion actions should also include engagement and awareness activities that will bring closer the audience. These may include some innovative actions such as podcasts, videocasts and short interviews. CODECO partners could be invited to answer specific standard questions (suggested or not by an audience) about the project itself or related subjects in the AI sector.

Webinars and online workshops will also be considered to engage and inform the public, stakeholders, and media channels about the project and its outcomes. YouTube videos (within the FOR YouTube channel - <https://www.youtube.com/@fortissTV/playlists> - or by the creation of a new, dedicated Youtube channel) and other multimedia content can be used to bring the research into action and make them more accessible to a wider audience. Videos can be posted on the project's website and shared on social media. Webinars to engage with stakeholders and experts covering topics related to the project might also be taken into consideration for CODECO members' attendance.

In addition to presenting research results, the CODECO team may also consider participating in panel discussions or interactive sessions in relevant meetings and events, such as those listed in Table 2 or others on AI field or related topics that allow attendees to engage with the project.

3.1.8 Collaborative Actions and Synergies

The CODECO project partners intend to collaborate with industry partners and academic institutions to promote its research results and to foster the development of new technologies and applications. The project also intends to establish a synchronised and close cooperation with relevant NGI, Cloud, and broader ICT initiatives, and relevant standards groups (e.g., IETF/IRTF) as well as with open-source initiatives (Linux Cloud Foundation). Such collaborations can provide access to new ideas, technologies, and resources, as well as create opportunities for knowledge exchange and cross learning. Collaborations formed with other partners during CODECO might also be continued in follow-up projects and support the establishment of new consortiums for future research projects.

Collaborations with industry can bring practical insights and real-world actions related to CODECO project, as well as provide opportunities for testing and validating project outcomes in real-world settings. The CODECO project members should collaborate with industry partners to develop the use cases, test, and evaluate the project's solutions, and receive feedback on their performance.

Collaborations with academia can provide access to the latest research and cutting-edge technologies, as well as opportunities for knowledge exchange and research findings transfer. All partners are encouraged to collaborate with academic institutions to publish research papers, develop new algorithms and techniques, and access specialized expertise and resources if needed.

To achieve this, the CODECO project will establish partnerships with relevant stakeholders, participate in industry events and conferences (see section 3.1.6), and engage with academic institutions and research organizations. The project partners can also organize joint workshops and seminars with industry and academic partners, establish joint research projects, and co-author publications to further promote synergies and partnership building.

3.2 Internal Strategy

3.2.1 Internal Communication

The success of a project largely depends on effective communication. Although it is extremely important to find collaborative ways to stay online to meet project demands, it is also quite important to efficiently manage information and summarize the key messages to

the corrected target recipients. As such, **e-mail messaging** will be used for regular communication between CODECO team members to share updates and information about the project. **Specific mailing lists** with specific partners and members were created dependently on the WP and tasks that they must participate in and/or are interested in, to directly target information. **This is further described in the D1 – Project Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines.**

Additionally, events and publication planned by the CODECO partners need to be communicated to the consortium 18 calendar days in advance. For CODECO consortium assistance, a reporting tool to collect information on planned events and planned publications is already shared in NextCloud repository, supervised by WP6 leader UGOE. **The Handbook of the project (D1) has detailed information on this.**

Effective internal communication can also help avoid misunderstandings, minimize conflicts, and increase the efficiency of project workflows. It can facilitate knowledge exchange and sharing of best practices among the CODECO consortium, enhancing the quality of project outputs. By encouraging open communication and feedback, CODECO partners can identify and address issues early on, which can mitigate risks and enable decision-making on time.

3.2.2 Project Meetings

The regular project meetings will be managed by the project coordinator (FOR) and the respective WP leaders and/or Task leaders if required. This will allow fruitful discussion about the project's progress, identification of issues, and make decisions.

In all internal meetings for the CODECO project, each partner should be represented at least by one member of the institution and shall participate cooperatively with every other member of the consortium. Four project plenary meetings per year are foreseen, two of those to take place in person and the other two as virtual meetings, as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Planned plenary meetings for the CODECO project for 2023.

CODECO plenary meeting	Date and Location
1 st CODECO plenary meeting – Kick-off meeting	16-17 January 2023 Munich, Germany
2 nd CODECO plenary meeting	4-5 April 2023 Virtual meeting

CODECO plenary meeting	Date and Location
3 rd CODECO plenary meeting	4-5 July 2023 Piraeus or Athens (TBD), Greece
4 th CODECO plenary meeting	11-13 December 2023 Virtual meeting

As stated in the CODECO deliverable D1 – Project Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines – partners will organize physical meetings on a rotational basis. These meetings will be aligned with the regular meetings of the Executive Board (EB) and Advisory Board (AB). Additional meetings may be arranged as needed based on the work plan and/or project needs. If physical meetings are not feasible due to exceptional circumstances, online meetings will be scheduled. For further detailed and guidelines on project meeting, **consider the D1 – Project Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines.**

3.2.3 Official Documentation

For effective and valuable dissemination of the CODECO project, it is essential to have well-designed layouts and templates. These materials will be used during the lifetime of the project, including deliverables, official documentation, conference presentations, and internal and external events. The objective is to establish a common visual identity for the project, ensuring a consistent graphical design across all related documents. As such, CODECO templates and layouts for official documentation (MS word format) and events presentations (MS PowerPoint format) are the following:

- MS Word format

The image shows three sample pages of MS Word format templates for CODECO. The first page is a title page with the CODECO logo, the title 'DX: TITLE', and version 'xx'. It includes a metadata table with fields like Work package, Task, Date, Submission date, Dissemination type, Deliverable, lead and editor, Contributing Partners, Version, Reviewer 1, and Reviewer 2. The second page is a Project Partners page listing logos of various companies like fortiss, INOVA+, Atos, etc. The third page is an Executive Summary page with a table for Document Revision History and a disclaimer.

Figure 5: CODECO project template of MS Word document.

- MS PowerPoint format

Figure 6: CODECO project template for presentations (.pptx).

Both official Word document layout and PowerPoint templates for the CODECO project must be mandatorily used in all official documents to be submitted, shared, or presented in all CODECO deliverables, documents, events, conferences, seminars, workshops, or other relevant situations.

In addition, as stated in the Grant Agreement of the project (n° 101092696) in ARTICLE 17 – COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY – under article 17.2 (Visibility - European flag and funding statement), communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the project including conferences, seminars and dissemination material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional platforms or social media, must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

Guidelines on disclaimers and acknowledgements are provided in D1 – Handbook.

4 Impact Measurement

D21 outlines the various activities that will be undertaken throughout the CODECO project's lifetime to disseminate actions and results and maximize its impact. These activities include, among others, the development of a project website, scientific publications, participation in conferences and events, social media engagement, and collaboration with industry and academia.

Table 6 outlines the impact measurement strategy that will be used to evaluate the effectiveness of these dissemination activities. A combination of quantitative and qualitative measures, including metrics such as website traffic, social media engagement, and attendance at events and conferences will be used. Qualitative methods will include surveys and interviews with stakeholders to gather feedback on the project's impact and to identify areas for improvement. The impact measurement strategy will be reviewed and updated on an ongoing basis to ensure that it remains relevant and effective in maximizing the project's impact. Detailed information and guides can also be found in the D1 – Project Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines.

Table 6: Table with dissemination activities for the CODECO project and their measures of impact.

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs	Lead
Project brochure	All	Dissemination of the project broadly	>100 per year	FOR
Project website	All	Dissemination and aggregator of all results	>500 visitors per year	WP6 team: FOR, INO, UGOE Inputs from all partners
Press releases	All	Dissemination of the overall project development, results, and events	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users	All partners
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals	1 per year	WP6 team: FOR, INO, UGOE All partners
Social networks	All	Facilitate communication and interaction with stakeholders, sharing of information and ideas, and community building.	>200 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn	INO Inputs from all partners
Industrial events	ICT, DEV, AR, GOV, SDO, EUS	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12), organised by FOR, aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	FOR
Development Events	AR, ICT, GOV, SDO	2 scientific events, a Dagstuhl seminar (UGOE) and a scientific workshop (ATH) co-located with a top conference from ACM/IEEE/IFIP	>50 participants	UGOE ATH

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs	Lead
		communities, both to be organized between year 2 and 3.		
Show-case event	All	A final showcase 1-day workshop, to be held in M34, jointly organised by FOR and INO, and aiming at show-casing the results to all target groups.	>70 participants	FOR INO
Standardization events	All	2 standardization events to be held in year 2 and year 3, jointly organised by IBM and FOR, aiming at discussing the standardization contributions of CODECO, together with other initiatives, e.g., Gaia-X, CSA EU-IoT, AIOTI.	>50 participants	IBM FOR
Scientific publications	AR, SDO, ICT, DEV	Report the CODECO scientific research and promote knowledge sharing and understanding. Regular submission of results in national, European, and international venues. CODECO shall target top venues, in particular IEEE, ACM and IFIP. CODECO shall also target European targets, such as EuCNC, CONASENSE. Publications will be made in open-science form, with papers being submitted in pre-print servers and relevant data on open repositories.	>40 peer-review, open access scientific papers	All partners

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs	Lead
Representation in external events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. Promotion of active participation and discussions on exploitation aspects and community building.	>50 events	All partners
Advanced training	ICT, AR, DEV	Transfer results and address potential gaps derived from interaction with the scientific community. Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops.	>20 organized training events with at least 50 participants	All research partners
Representation in committees	AR, ICT	CODECO will actively participate in conferences closely related to CODECO across ACM, IEEE, IFIP. Several of the consortium members have been continuous contributors to these conference series, including as general-, program-, workshops.	>20 committees per year	All partners
Demonstrations	All	Project partners will also actively participate in demo sessions held at major conferences, workshops, and standardization meetings (e.g., IETF, 3GPP, ETSI MEC ISG, 5GAA, Networld2020 meeting) to show-case the results of CODECO, provide tutorials, demos, etc..	At least 3 demonstrations per year, starting on year 2.	Use-case partners

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs	Lead
SDO liaison and monitoring	SDO, IN, AR, GOV	Based on T6.3, assist the wider impact of CODECO via concrete contributions to SDOs (event organization, white papers, standards).	>10 contributions	All partners
Exploitation workshops	CODECO consortium	2 internal events shall be organised to address exploitation aspects in year 2 and year 3 (WP7). These events shall be dedicated to discussion on exploitation aspects, being organized by the WP7 task leaders (INO, ECL, ALM), and shall involve the CODECO AB as well as eventual external stakeholders.	>20 participants per event, 2 events	WP7 task leaders: INO, ECL, ALM
Hackathon/Demo Camp	AR, ICT, DEV	1 demo camp/Hackathon, to be jointly organized by ECL and INO in the context of the exploitation activities and community building (WP7), by M24	>70 participants	ECL INO

Legend: ICT: Information and communication technologies companies; SME: Small and medium-sized enterprises; GOV: government, public authorities, and policymakers; SDO: Standardization entities and open-source communities; AR: Academic and research institutions; EUS: End-users; DEV: Software developers; GA: General audience who might be interested in the project.

The CODECO project dissemination measures will be followed by the Deliverable 22 – Dissemination, Promotion, Scientific Outreach and Standardisation report – in which the progress of the project will be presented concerning KPIs and achieved actions, as well as the future for the following months.

5 Summary and Next Steps

The major goal of this deliverable is to create awareness among CODECO team members for the importance of a good communication and dissemination methodology, by providing a list of all communication and promotion activities planned for the project. This will certainly boost the success of the CODECO project as it provides a framework for sharing project outcomes and engaging with relevant stakeholders. Such a plan can enhance the visibility and impact of project outcomes, create opportunities for knowledge exchange and collaboration, and facilitate the uptake and exploitation of project results. CODECO can only reach its major performance capacity if an efficient communication network is built.

In the upcoming months and years of the project, it is expected that all CODECO partners establish a clear and consistent message about the project, build trust and credibility, ensure the widest engagement of stakeholders, and adoption of results across different domains. The exploitation beyond the project lifetime is envisioned to support larger-scale exploitation of the CODECO assets and ecosystem. This considers not only the individual assets of each partner/organization but also synergies across the consortium.

During the lifetime of the project, it is important to regularly review and update the dissemination plan to reflect the project's progress and changes in stakeholder needs. This can include developing new communication materials, engaging with new stakeholders, adapting communication strategies to respond to emerging trends and challenges, and participating in distinct and more relevant public events. By regularly reviewing and updating the plan, the CODECO project can ensure that its dissemination and communication activities remain relevant to the community.

The implementation of these dissemination measures will be monitored throughout the project and then followed by Dissemination, Promotion, Scientific Outreach and Standardisation reports on M18 (June 2024) and M36 (December 2025) by UGOE, which will provide the

reporting on the dissemination, promotion, scientific outreach, and standardization initiatives concerning the project.

6 References

- [1] https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

